

CONSILIENCE

Principles

Fierce electrochemical energies burn in neurophysiological frontal synapses of those highly active brains attempting to integrate General Relativity and Quantum Mechanics. Individuals thus engaging their brains range from Nobel prize-winning physicists through philosophers and biologists studying consciousness, to keenly interested laypeople, to similarly interested children. Conciliation¹ of the infinitesimally small with the astronomically gigantic views of the physical universe consumes much brainpower of all children of Cosmos.

Beyond intellectual titillation, what practical value results from deep study that integrates pre-quantum sources and quantum mechanics with General Relativity? Consider here what and where we exist in an otherwise meaningless universe. This study demonstrates consilience as a protocol of protocols. Posits intrinsic purpose and value, and places them higher than knowledge accumulation for the sake of knowledge or for the sake of technology, while it simultaneously advances those.

Methodology

“Consilience” here refers to a fundamental protocol based in reliance on intrinsic intelligence¹ of underlying unity in the natural world, by which one can fruitfully engage interdisciplinary study. That is, one can derive protocols for inquiry from one’s underlying fundamental assumption. Such inquiry permits prediction for purposes of concomitant variation, and provides basic scientific method to determine causal relationships.

Restated more briefly, this study emphasizes a protocol of protocols for discovery. Results speak for themselves. See also, Universal Scalar Mind in the sense of consciousness².

Tools & Evidentiary Results

Architectural exploration of universal scalar fields in which one exists and participates enables identification and investigation of fundamental principles. Tools! The protocol extends one’s ability to explore viable solutions to modern scientific and engineering quandaries - and, logically following, social problems³.

Consider standpoints of physical sciences (especially physics and chemistry), psychology, philosophy of science, and molecular biology. While scientific methodology guides this

¹ John Read, *Intrinsic Intelligence & Common Science* 2020, <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/8n5bz>

² per Max Planck’s often quoted, “I regard consciousness as fundamental. I regard matter as derivative from consciousness. ... Everything that we talk about, everything that we regard as existing, postulates consciousness.” And again, “There is no matter as such. All matter originates and exists only by virtue of a force which brings the particle of an atom to vibration and holds this most minute solar system of the atom together. We must assume behind this force the existence of a conscious and intelligent mind. This mind is the matrix of all matter.” *Das Wesen der Materie* (1944)

³ as a side note, any and all problems of material civilization, including climate change, have real and proximate solutions. These solutions do not account, as yet, for social and cultural barriers.

study, these principles extend beyond science, and demonstrate a purposeful understanding of universal architecture – the architecture one inhabits, and in which one actively participates and creates.

Principles & Value

This architectural exercise elucidates Universal Scalar Logic and Consilience as fundamental working principles for any rigorous and interdisciplinary study of the universe and of the mind – especially larger life of the mind. It demonstrates means by which one can connect actions and processes at any and all levels. If this has value – and it does to me – of what does that value consist? Universal Scalar Logic and Consilience provide exquisite tools.

Self Similarity

Millions of people for thousands of years have looked at earthly and astronomical bodies as globular or spherical. While those views function to a point, this analysis utilizes fractal geometric architectures as tools – especially the geometry Laurent Nottale’s thorough fractal mapping to Riemann’s geometry (that Einstein used in his general field equations⁴) – these tools reveal structural working principles at all scales, pre-quantum through cosmological. Other self-similar architectures – fractal and toroidal – with solid mathematical grounding, and much empirical evidence, work to the same purpose⁵.

Scale Relativity

Scale relativity proposes that space and time have self-similar structure, and demonstrably unify quantum mechanics and relativity. Clearly, this has major cosmological implications.

Quantum mechanics and relativity consider physical reality from different directions and scales. Fractal geometries provide mathematical tools whereby one can describe both quantum and relativistic phenomena, and demonstrate their unity.

At both deeper and at higher levels than quantum and astrophysical, one can observe that fractal geometry appears spontaneously in quantum and astrophysical phenomena, demonstrating a fundamental aspect of Universal Scalar Logic – target of this treatment

Self-Similar Implications

All self-similar architectural aspects, by virtue of Universal scalar interpenetration, assume dynamic structures whereby any change at any level affects all levels.

⁴ The very purpose he intended.

⁵ this exercise also references the work of Leonard Susskind and Gerard 't Hooft on holographic principle, and John Wheeler’s work in quantum foam. Likewise, Susie Vrobel and her colleagues at the Institute for Fractal Research.

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Thus, the quote, “thou canst not pluck a flower without troubling a star.”⁶. Certainly not a novel observation, this has basis in the fractal nature of the universe. What one does makes a difference to everyone anywhere, irrespective of scale.

This fractal structure gives rise to the quantum-relativistic effects one can observe in nature.

Examples

Fractal galaxies: details of the shape change as the scale changes. Consider the galaxy known as the Pinwheel Galaxy. The overall shape of the galaxy remains the same at all scales, but the details of the shape change as scale changes.

[Link Opens in a new window](#) **Fractal galaxy**

- **Fractal clouds:** details of shape change as scale changes.

Ubiquitous, billowing cumulus cloud.

Generated and Natural Fractal Clouds

Cumulonimbus

⁶ From "*The Mistress of Vision*" by Francis Thompson.

- **Fractal patterns in electron orbitals:** Electron orbitals demark the regions an atom's electrons occupy. Commonly, scientists depict electrons as smooth, continuous shapes. Recent research shows electron orbitals as fractals and toroids.

- For example, the electron orbital known as the hydrogen 1s has fractal shape. Overall shape of the orbital remains the same at all scales. Details of shape change as scale changes.

Fractal electron orbitals

- Fractal patterns in the behavior of atomic particles: Subatomic particles, such as electrons and photons, exhibit behavior described by quantum mechanics. This otherwise unpredictable behavior illustrates fractal structure of space-time. For example, fractal patterns describe the behavior of electrons in quantum dots.

Fractal electron orbitals in two dimensions ⁷

- In electron orbitals where electrons likely appear in regions around an atom, one can imagine orbitals as spherical. This functions, but fractal models work better. E.g., the electron orbitals of hydrogen atoms show fractal self-similarity.

⁷ Design and characterization of electrons in a fractal geometry, Kempkes, S.N., Slot, M.R., Freeney, S.E., et al. 2019, Nat. Phys. 15, 127–131 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-018-0328-0>

How Scale Relativity Works:

In scale relativity, the fractal structure of space-time describes changes in relationships of laws of physics as scale changes, hierarchically. It does not posit one as more fundamental than another, given scale.

At quantum scale, the laws of physics exhibit quantum mechanical parameters. The classical scale appears at the largest scale in the hierarchy. At the classical scale, the laws of physics appear, well.... classical.

Laws of physics at intermediate scales mix quantum and classical physics and we can see quantum-relativistic effects at these scales even using human sensory apparatus such as sight and sound, even in the absence of technological sensors. Consider, for example, a green leaf. We see a green reflected at Quantum levels by chloroplasts. Our eyes suffice!

4 & 5 Dimensional Moments

While it may seem redundant to repeat⁸, one must keep in mind that spacetime's fractal architecture of the universe includes time as well as space. Time provides fractal architecture extension in four dimensions. This has momentous implications regarding what we consider as moments, conscious and underlying.

"The past isn't dead; it isn't even past" – William Faulkner⁹

This unification describes space-time as a 4-dimensional non-differentiable continuum. Consciousness represents 5th dimension, also as nondifferentiable continuum.

This perspective enables one to observe one's identity in, and purposeful manipulation of, moments¹⁰, It provides one with volitional power.

- For example, quantum mechanics model wave-particle duality, wherein objects behave as both waves and particles. The fractal nature of space-time describes so-called wave-particle duality as non-dual, as objects make up smaller and smaller wave-like self-similar structures as one zooms closer.
- Relativity describes gravity, where objects attract each other by a force that increases with their mass. This force of gravity describes the fractal nature of spacetime, as one sees objects embedded in a sea of smaller and smaller gravitational fields as one zooms in closer.

Scale Relativity unifies quantum mechanics and relativity by demonstrating that space-time consists of an infinite number of self-similar parts, which gives rise to the seeming wave-particle duality of quantum mechanics, and provides a single, logical framework for both.

⁸ figuratively and literally...

⁹ "Requiem for a Nun," 1951.

¹⁰ holistic composite structures, defined in detail in a subsequent section.

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No smooth curves exist in quantum space-time. In quantum mechanics, space-time consists of an infinite number of self-similar forces that go by various names – quarks, gluons, electrons, neutrinos, positrons, and the like. An ever-growing menagerie...

Where classical physics represents particles as point-like objects, in Erwin Schrödinger's and Einstein's quantum mechanics, wavefunctions describe vortices of highly concentrated energy. Such wavefunctions spread over space-time, and can augment and interfere with one another.

Uncertainty

For example, Nottale's fractal geometry graphically describes the uncertainty principle. The uncertainty principle states that it is impossible to know both the position and momentum of a particle with perfect accuracy. Position and momentum do not describe separate aspects, because the wavefunction of a particle spreads out over both space and time...They do not mathematically differentiate.

Examine a graphic example of how fractal geometry explains the wave-particle duality of quantum mechanics.

The wavepacket in this image depicts a wave spread out over a region of spacetime. The wavepacket has a certain amount of momentum and coherence, but no single point describes its position. I prefer this clearer viewpoint to Heisenberg's description.

Standard coastline examples: the pedestrian example of coastlines illustrates the wave-particle duality of quantum mechanics. Imagine a fractal coastline. The coastline consists of an infinite number of self-similar parts. This means that it is impossible to draw a smooth curve that follows the coastline exactly. Instead, one can only draw jagged and irregular curves. The smaller the scale, the more so.

Fractal geometries revolutionize one's understanding of the universe – and of oneself. Architecturally unifying quantum mechanics and relativity provides experiential foundations for physics, and for consciousness.

Fractal coastlines extended

One can think of the wavefunction of a particle as a fractal coastline. One cannot know the exact position of “particles¹¹”, since the quantity spreads out over a region of spacetime. Thus, particles can exhibit wave-like properties, such as interference. The image of the fractal coastline presents a simplified example. Considering wavefunctions of particles describes more complex natures.

Using that analogy, one can imagine the wavefunction of a particle comparable to a fractal coastline. One cannot know the exact position of a particle because the particle spreads out over a region of space-time. Thus, particles exhibit wave-like properties, such as interference.

One can visualize such a graphic example to understand the so-called Uncertainty Principle.

One can't know the exact position of the wavepacket, because it doesn't have one – the wavepacket occupies continuous positions across a region of both space and time.

Put the above – at least for the moment – in the context of a nondeterministic universe.

Laurent Nottell¹²'s Architectural Structures & Frank Wilczek's Atomic Creation
Laurent Nottell's fractal geometry creates a framework for unified description of quantum mechanics and general relativity.

Frank Wilczek's descriptions of quantum chromodynamics (QCD) also use fractal geometry to show how the strong force holds quarks together to form matter.

The two approaches of Nottell and Wilczek complement one another. Nottell's approach provides a general framework for unifying quantum mechanics and general relativity, while Wilczek's approach provides a specific way to apply this framework to QCD exposition of matter creation.

By unifying Nottell's fractal integration with Wilczek's descriptions of QCD, one can create a unified theory of quantum gravity¹³, which in turn will provide a single framework for understanding all of the fundamental forces of nature.

Technology

A unified theory of quantum gravity provides a single framework for understanding all of the fundamental forces of nature, inevitably leading to a broad spectrum of new technologies.

- **Medical research:** A unified theory of quantum gravity eliminates force distinctions separating mind from matter, and conciliates understanding the human body.

¹¹ considered here as extremely concentrated energetic vortices.

¹² One could also use Susie Vrobel's fractal descriptions.

¹³ For purposes of simplification, this brief does not include Carlo Rovelli's and others "gravitons" vortices, or so-called "Quantum Loop Gravity", as beyond the scope of this exposition.

- **Information technology:** Approaching information at gravitational level will revolutionize the way we process information, and lead to new applications in artificial intelligence and cryptography.
- **Space exploration:** A unified theory of quantum gravity can provide structures to understand black holes, neutron stars, and other exotic objects in space. This will likely lead to new ways to explore space and to develop new technologies for space travel.
- **Energy production:** A unified theory of quantum gravity – finally bringing all fundamental forces together – leads to new ways to generate and store already characterized energy.

New forms of energy: A unified theory of quantum gravity leads to currently uncharacterized massive new energetic forms. For example, we know there exists a fifth fundamental force of nature, called the "dark force." Empirical evidence for this existence comes in the form of anomalous gravities. The dark force (and so-called "dark matter") exerts vast gravitational influence on normal matter and normal force such as light, electron beams, etc.

Appendices

Context in a nondeterministic universe. Regimes

Nondeterministic, Deterministic, Superdeterministic Regimes

Pay Your Money, Take Your Chances.

A nondeterministic universe (our subject choice here, and my favorite) represents an open-ended future, with multiple possible outcomes for any variable-given event based on choice of regime.

This sharply contrasts a deterministic universe, where only one possible outcome derives from any given event. Or in a super deterministic universe, no variables exist.

Everything Changes

Since everything changes, this nondeterministic view allows one to have one's cake and eat it too. One can imagine a super deterministic universe in one moment, and in the next moment¹⁴, a different super deterministic universe¹⁵, and interpenetrating moments.

¹⁴ depending on one's understanding of moments as events.

¹⁵ this juxtaposition probably will not satisfy Mike Moran's super determinism. In that view, following Kurt Vonnegut Jr., the Tralfamadoreans' test pilot has always pushed the button that will destroy the universe, even though the test pilot knows that it will, and does not intend to destroy the universe.

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Fractal geometry can illustrate the architectural nature of the universe, but not the above choices. No single scale exists at which one can fully grok the universe. Rather, one can understand the universe as a complex system of interacting regimes.

In the nondeterministic universe covered here, conscious creatures can exhibit free will, because they comprise and represent nondifferentiable integrals in the larger and smaller universe. Even though one can represent the system as a whole, it does not put one's fingers on all the tabs.

Again, this represents architectural unification, not field equation unification.

Attitudes present one with control mechanisms.

An Anecdote Regarding Attitude

In 1979 in Marin County, California, I spent an afternoon with Leland Spelman Sr, for a celebration. He had served as pre-WW2 deputy district attorney for the city of Vienna.

When Nazis took Austria they removed him, a Jew, from power and sent him to a concentration camp. Over a period of five years, he stayed as a prisoner in every major Nazi death camp, carrying bodies of his fellows from gas chambers to ovens, and then the burnt remains to ditches for burial.

He lived with hope. In 1944 Nazi authorities unexpectedly released him from Auschwitz, and sent him by train, with papers indicating no Judaism, to Zürich. The Nazi commandant of Auschwitz gave him traveling money. Why?

His former colleagues in the Atty. Gen.'s office in Vienna never gave up, and eventually secured his release. In Zürich he went to a bank in which he had a pre-war account, withdrew money, traveled to Ireland, and thence to the United States. The day I met him, a man in his mid-90s, he had just been reinstated as deputy district attorney for Vienna.

Appendix 0 – Variables

Additional thoughts on the architectural construction of the universe:

- One cannot predict the future with perfect accuracy. One can make relatively accurate predictions about the future based on one's understanding of universal laws at all levels and at any given scale, and the current state of the universe.
- Nondeterministic nature of the universe also means that one has abilities to make choices that affect the past and future in all directions. One's choices influence the course of events, and they influence a better or worse future for oneself and the larger universe.
- Nondeterministic nature of the universe means that one has power to shape one's own destiny, even though one cannot control everything that happens to one – at least individually.

Toroids and fractal geometric shapes exhibit self-similarity. This means that they interactively break down or up into smaller or larger parts of similar shape to the whole.

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Toroids have three-dimensional shapes that resemble donuts. Fractals geometric shapes exhibit infinite complexity and self-similarity at all scales.

One finds toroids and fractals throughout nature. For example, the shape of a torus can be seen in the structure of atoms, the shapes of lightning, the vertebrate heart, and the solar system. Fractals can be seen in the shapes of mountains, coastlines, and snowflakes.

Another connection between toroids and fractals links them to the concept of energy. Toroids and fractals efficiently function to store, distribute, and transfer energy.

Simple examples of how toroids and fractals appear in nature:

- **Atoms:** The electron cloud around an atom shape as fractals and as a torus.
- **Human heart:** The four-chambered organ we call a heart exhibits toroidal electrical field.
- **Solar system:** The solar system exhibits fractal like similarities in planetary nesting, and a hierarchical structure like the branches of a fractal tree.
- **Mountains:** Mountains often have fractal-like shapes, with smaller mountains branching off larger mountains.
- **Coastlines:** Coastlines have fractal-like shapes, with small inlets and peninsulas branching off of larger coastlines.
- **Snowflakes:** Snowflakes have fractal-like shapes, with each flake made up of smaller flakes.

A few other fractal architectures that have been proposed to unify quantum scale with astrophysical scale. One such architecture is the **holographic principle**, which states that the information contained in a region of spacetime is holographically encoded on its boundary. This means that the entire universe could be represented as a hologram, with all of its information contained on the surface of a sphere.

String theory landscape provides a fractal architecture representing a vast and complex space of possible string theories. Each point in this space represents a different possible universe, with different laws of physics and different values for the fundamental constants.

In so-called quantum spacetime, discrete fractal units make spacetime itself. Nottell's fractals incorporate this concept.

Quantum foam describes a hypothetical subatomic level of reality made up of tiny quantum fluctuations, fractal in nature.

Appendix 2 – including logical Python snippets derived from Google Bard

Deductive script snippet

Quantum mechanics and relativity are unified by fractal geometry.
Fractal geometry is a geometry of self-similarity,
Wherein objects have similar structure at different scales.

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This self-similarity allows for the unification of quantum mechanics and relativity, As both theories can be seen as describing different aspects of the same underlying reality.

Comparison Nottell fractal architecture and the holographic principle in terms of consistency with empirical evidence:

Nottell Fractal Architecture

- **Proposed by:** Laurent Nottell
- **Basic idea:** The universe exhibits fractal structure, with the self-same structure repeating at different scales.
- **Empirical evidence:** shows that galactic clusters arrange in fractal patterns.

Holographic Principle

Leonard Susskind and Gerard 't Hooft propose that the boundary of a region of space encodes the information of that region, as though it were a discrete object. Observation: black holes behave as if they have a holographic surface.

Nottell's fractal architecture and the holographic principle both exemplify Universal Scalar Logic, and empirical evidence suggests that both theories work synergistically.

Fibonacci

Fibonacci sequence can describe the growth of plants and animals, the arrangement of leaves on a stem, and the spiral patterns of galaxies. This bespeaks universal scalar architecture, as well as consilience.

Compare these Models to Quantum Foam

Along lines of Einstein's and Schrödinger's hidden variables, quantum foam provides a hypothetical subatomic structure *beneath* quantum mechanics made up of tiny, interconnected "bubbles", now empirically observed (though not with that term). These bubbles provide fluctuations in space-time that give rise to quantum phenomena, including extending cosmic density in spite of cosmic expansion.

Just as the Nottell fractal architecture and the holographic principle attempt to unify quantum mechanics and general relativity, Quantum Foam presents a more literal view of the quantum nature of space-time. It proposes tiny physical bubbles of space-time. The Nottell fractal architecture and the holographic principle present more general interpretations based in correlations of self-similar principles. Rather than literal physical bubbles, they propose that the information in space-time encodes in fractal patterns (Nottell) or on its boundary. The three models mutually include each other.

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This table summarizes the comparison between three models:

Feature	Quantum Foam	Nottell Fractal Architecture	Holographic Principle
<i>Proposed by</i>	<i>John Wheeler</i>	<i>Laurent Nottell</i>	<i>Leonard Susskind and Gerard 't Hooft</i>
Basic idea	Tiny bubbles of space-time makeup large space-time.	The fractal universe has a self-same structure repeating at all scales. Evident in many studies, including the famous coastline study.	The information in a region of space encodes on its boundary.
Consistency with empirical evidence	Relationship between hypothetical model and density of matter in an expanding universe.	Conciliant evidence based on relations between fractal and Fibonacci sequence.	Quantum optics, 1999 Princeton University demonstrates this with a cesium plasma and laser pulsed sign waves.

No scientifically verified *graphic* examples of quantum foam exist, since quantum foam itself exists as a hypothetical sub-subatomic structure at Planck scales, smaller than anything that one can observe. Perhaps equivalent to Anaximander's One. Empirical examples do exist in the relationship between cosmic physical density, and universal expansion.

John Wheeler, the first physicist to propose the idea of quantum foam, created the following image of what quantum foam might look like, as tiny bubbles at Planck scale that constantly pop in and out of existence.

Impression of quantum foam by John Wheeler
 Hyperlink [opens in a new window](#)

The image shows a series of tiny bubbles that appear interconnected in a complex network.

ⁱ Francis Bacon, the English philosopher, statesman (purser to Queen Elizabeth I, and ostensibly her lover), scientist, and author of the "Novum Organum", used the term "conciliation" in the context of methodology and protocols for empirical inquiry now known as the scientific method.

Bacon used the term "conciliation" in the following ways:

Conciliation of Nature: Bacon emphasized the need for scientists to engage in the "conciliation of nature." By which he meant that scientists should seek to reconcile and harmonize the diverse phenomena and observations based on an assumption or postulate of underlying unity in the natural world. This involved collecting data in an interdisciplinary context, conducting experiments, and drawing general principles to unify and make sense of the observed phenomena.

Errors of Idols: Bacon identified what he called "idols" as various sources of errors and biases that could distort human understanding of nature. Bacon's approach involved the conciliation of these idols, which meant recognizing their influence, and overcoming them to achieve a more accurate understanding of the natural world.

Integration of Empirical Data: Bacon believed that scientists should gather facts and data from a wide range of sources, carefully analyze them, and synthesize them into a unified and reliable body of knowledge.

E.O. Wilson and Conciliation:

Context: Edward O. "Snake" Wilson, preeminent 20th and 21st-century biologist and ecologist, used the term "conciliation" in a cultural context of his work on biodiversity conservation and sociobiology. He also wrote a more general book, entitled *Consilience*.

Method: Wilson based his methodology on a postulate of underlying unity in the natural world. As with Francis Bacon, this involved collecting data in an interdisciplinary context, conducting experiments, and drawing general principles to unify and make sense of the observed phenomena. Wilson's approach to conciliation involved interdisciplinary research and collaboration, bringing together experts from various fields, including physics, chemistry, biology, ecology, sociology, and economics, to address the complex challenges of biodiversity conservation in a world where human activities often threaten natural habitats.